

A Note on Strongly Large Ideals

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 01 July 2024	In this paper, I introduced Strongly Large Ideals and studied some properties. In this paper, I also studied Strongly Large Closed ideals and Strongly Large Complement Ideal. An Ideal is called an SL-Closed ideal if it has no proper Strongly Large Extension in L. I prove that direct summands of a lattice L are SL-Closed ideals. I give an example for, the intersection of SL-Closed ideals of a lattice L need not be SL-closed. I also show that , direct summands of SL-Complements are SL-Complements.
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KEYWORDS: Ideal, Essential Ideal, Closed Ideal, Strongly Large Ideals, Strongly Large Closed ideal and Strongly Large Complement Ideal	

I. INTRODUCTION

Inaam Hadi and Thaar Younis Ghawi[] introduced the concepts of a Strongly Large submodule. B. Ungor, S. Halicioglu, M.A. Kamal and A. Harmanci[] introduced the concept a Strongly Large Closed submodule and a Strongly Large Complement submodule. A submodule K of an R-Module M is called a strongly large submodule in M, if for any $m \in M, s \in R$ with $ms \neq 0$ there exists an $r \in R$ such that $mr \in K$ and $mrs \neq 0$. A submodule N of R-module M is called SL-closed if, N has no proper strongly large extensions in M. A Submodule K is called an SL-complement in M if there exists a submodule L such that K is an SL-Complement of L in M.

In this paper, I introduced Strongly Large Ideals and studied Closed ideals and Strongly Large Complement Ideal. An Ideal is called an SL-Closed ideal if it has no proper Strongly Large Extension in L. I prove that direct summands of a lattice L are SL-Closed ideals. I give an example for, the intersection of SL-Closed ideals of a lattice L need not be SL-closed. I also show that , direct summands of SL-Complements are SL-Complements.

Throughout in this paper L denotes a lattice with 0 and 1. $Id(L)$ denotes the ideal lattice.

II. STRONGLY LARGE IDEALS

Definition 1 : Strongly large ideals : Let $I \in Id(L)$ is called a Strongly Large Ideal in L, in case for any $a, b \in L$ with $a \wedge b \neq 0$ there exists $c \in L$ such that $a \wedge c \in I$ and $a \wedge b \wedge c \neq 0$. It is denoted by SL-ideals

Definition 2: Strongly large closed ideal: An ideal $I \in Id(L)$ is called strongly large closed ideal if I has no proper

strongly large extension in L. It is denoted by SL-closed ideal.

Figure 1

In the lattice shown in figure 1, Let $I = \{0, a, b, c, e\}$, for $e, g \in L$ such that $e \wedge g = c \neq 0$ there exists $f \in L$ such that $e \wedge f = b \in I$ and $e \wedge g \wedge f = a \neq 0$. Thus I is strongly large ideal in L. Similarly $J = \{0, a, d, g, c\}$ is also strongly large ideal in L. In the lattice shown in figure 2, there does not exists any strongly large ideal in L.

Figure 2

Lemma 1: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \subseteq J$. If I is strongly large in J then $I \cap J = (0)$ implies $J \cap K = (0)$ for any ideal K of L .

Proof: Suppose $I \in \text{Id}(L)$ is strongly large in J . Let $K \in \text{Id}(L)$ be such that $I \cap K = (0)$. Clearly $I \cap K \in \text{Id}(J)$ and $I \cap (J \cap K) = (0)$ and so $(J \cap K) = (0)$.

Lemma 2: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \subseteq J$. Then I is strongly large in J and J is strongly large in L then I is strongly large in L .

Proof: Let $a, b \in L$ be such that $a \wedge b \neq 0$. Since J is strongly large in L , there exists $c_2 \in J$ such that $a \wedge c_1 \wedge c_2 \in I$ with $a \wedge b \wedge c_1 \wedge c_2 \neq 0$. Hence I is strongly large in L .

Lemma 3: Let L be a lattice. If I_1 is strongly large in J_1 and I_2 is strongly large in J_2 then $I_1 \cap I_2$ is strongly large in $J_1 \cap J_2$.

Proof: Let $a, b \in J_1 \cap J_2$ with $a \wedge b \neq 0$ then there exists $c_1 \in J_1 \cap J_2$ such that $a \wedge c_1 \in I_1$ and $a \wedge b \wedge c_1 \neq 0$. If $a \wedge c_1 \in I_2$ then prove is over. If $a \wedge c_1$ does not belong to I_2 , Observe that $a \wedge c_1 \in J_2$ with $a \wedge b \wedge c_1 \neq 0$. So there exists $c_2 \in J_2$ such that $a \wedge c_1 \wedge c_2 \in I_2$ and $a \wedge b \wedge c_1 \wedge c_2 \neq 0$. Hence $a \wedge c_1 \wedge c_2 \in I_1 \cap I_2$ with $a \wedge b \wedge c_1 \wedge c_2 \neq 0$. Therefore $I_1 \cap I_2$ is strongly large in $J_1 \cap J_2$.

Lemma 4: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \subseteq J$. Then I is strongly large in L if and only if I is strongly large in J and J is strongly large in L .

Proof: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \subseteq J$. Since I is strongly large in J and J is strongly large in L then by Lemma 2, I is strongly large in L .

Conversely, Suppose that I is strongly large in L . To show that I is strongly large in J and J is strongly large in L . By Lemma 3, I is strongly large in L implies $I \cap J$ is strongly large in $L \cap J$ implies I is strongly large in J . Now let $a, b \in L$ be such that $a \wedge b \neq 0$. Since I is strongly large in L there exists $c \in L$ such that $a \wedge c \in I$ and $a \wedge b \wedge c \neq 0$. Since $I \subseteq J$ we have $a \wedge c \in J$ with $a \wedge b \wedge c \neq 0$. Hence J is strongly large in L .

Lemma 5: Direct summands of a lattice L are SL-closed ideals.

Proof: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ be such that $L = I \oplus J$. Assume that I is strongly large in $K \in \text{Id}(L)$. Hence $K \cap J = (0)$ by lemma

1 and so $K = I$. Therefore I has no proper strongly large extension in L .

Remark: The intersection of SL-closed ideals of a lattice L need not be SL-closed.

Theorem 1: Let L be a lattice and $I \in \text{Id}(L)$ be an SL-closed ideal in L . If K is strongly large in L then $I \cap K$ is SL-closed.

Proof: Let $J \in \text{Id}(L)$ be a strongly large extension of $I \cap K$ in L that is $I \cap K$ is strongly large in J in L . To show: $I \cap K$ is SL-closed in L i.e. $I \cap K = J$. To show I is strongly large in J . Let $a, b \in I \cap J$ be such that $a \wedge b \neq 0$. Since K is strongly large in L , there exists $c \in L$ such that $a \wedge c \in K$ and $a \wedge b \wedge c \neq 0$. So $a \wedge c \in I \cap K$ and hence $a \wedge b \wedge c \in J$ with $a \wedge b \wedge c \neq 0$. Since $I \cap K$ is strongly large in J , there exists $c_1 \in J$ such that $a \wedge b \wedge c \wedge c_1 \in I \cap K \subseteq I$ and $a \wedge b \wedge c \wedge c_1 \neq 0$. Therefore I is strongly large in J . Since I is an SL-closed in L , it follows that $I = I \cap J$. Hence $I \cap K = J$ and so $I \cap K$ is an SL-closed in L .

Definition 3: SL-Complement: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \cap J = (0)$. Then J is called SL-complement of I in L if J is an SL-closed in L and $I \oplus J$ is strongly large in L .

An Ideal $I \in \text{Id}(L)$ is called SL-complement in L if there exists an ideal $J \in \text{Id}(L)$ such that I is an SL-complement of J in L .

Theorem 2: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \cap J = (0)$. Then J is an SL-complement of I in L if and only if J is maximal with respect to being $J \oplus I$ strongly large in M .

Proof: Let J be an SL-complement of I in L and $J \subseteq K \in L$ with $K \oplus I$ strongly large in L . Let $P, Q \in \text{Id}(K)$ with $P \cap Q \neq (0)$. There exists $R \in \text{Id}(L)$ such that $P \cap R \in J \oplus I$ and $P \cap Q \cap R \neq (0)$. Then $P \cap R \in \text{Id}(J)$. Hence J is strongly large in K . Since J is SL-closed in L , we have $J = K$. This shows the maximality of J with respect to being $J \oplus I$ strongly large in M .

Conversely, Let J be maximal with respect to being $J \oplus I$ strongly large in L and K be strongly large extension of J in L . Then $J \cap K = (0)$ and hence by Lemma 4, $K \oplus I$ is strongly large in M . By the maximality of J , $J = K$, Therefore J is SL-closed in L and J is an SL-complement of I in L .

Theorem 3: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$. If J is an SL-complement of I in L , then J is a complement of I in L .

Proof: Let $K \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $J \subseteq K$ and $I \cap K = (0)$. Since L is a strongly large extension of $J \oplus I$, $K \oplus J$ is a strongly large ideal of L by Lemma 4. So we have $J=K$ from Theorem 2. Hence J is maximal with respect to being $I \cap J = (0)$.

Remark: Complements need not be SL-Complements.

Theorem 4: Let $K \in \text{Id}(L)$ be an SL-complement of $I \in \text{Id}(L)$ and $K = K_1 \oplus K_2$ then K_1 is an SL-complement of $K_2 \oplus I$ in L . In particular, direct summands of SL-complements are SL-complements.

Proof: Let $P \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $K_1 \subseteq P$ and $P \oplus K_2 \oplus I$ is strongly large in L . Then $K = K_1 \oplus K_2 \subseteq P \oplus K_2$. Since K is maximal with respect to being $K \oplus I$ strongly large in L , then $K = K_1$

$\oplus K_2 = P \oplus K_2$. So $K_1 = P$. Thus by Theorem 2, K_1 is an SL-complement of $K_2 \oplus I$ in L .

Theorem 5: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$. If I is an SL-complement in J and J is an SL-complement in L then J contains every strongly large extension of I in L .

Proof: Let I be an SL-complement of an ideal I' in J and J be an SL-complement of an ideal J' in L . By Theorem 2, I is maximal in J with respect to $I' \oplus I$ strongly large in J and J is maximal in L with respect to $J' \oplus J$ strongly closed in L . Let $K \in \text{Id}(L)$ be a strongly large extension of I in L . Now since $I \subseteq (K \oplus J') \cap J \subseteq J$ and $[(K \oplus J') \cap J] \oplus I'$ is strongly large in J , we have $(K \oplus J') \cap J = I$. We know that $(K \vee J) \cap J' = 0$. It is clear that L is a strongly large extension of $(K \vee J) \oplus J'$. By the maximality of J , we have $K \vee J$ and so $K \subseteq J$.

Theorem 6: Let $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \subseteq J$, If $K \in \text{Id}(L)$ is an SL-complement of I in L then $K \cap J$ is an SL-complement of I in J .

Proof: Since $K \oplus I$ is strongly large in L by Lemma 3 $(K \oplus I) \cap J = (K \cap J) \oplus I$ is strongly large in J . We show that $K \cap J$ is an SL-closed in J . Let $P \in \text{Id}(L)$ be strongly large extension of $K \cap J$ in J . Then $(K \vee P) \cap I = (K \vee P) \cap J \cap I = [(K \cap J) \vee P] \cap I = P \cap I = (0)$, It is clear that $(K \vee P) \oplus I$ is strongly large in L and hence $K = K \vee P$ by the maximality of K . Thus $P = K \cap J$ and therefore $K \cap J$ is an SL-closed ideal of J .

Corollary 1: $I, J \in \text{Id}(L)$ with $I \subseteq J$. If I is an SL-complement of J and J is an SL-complement in L then I is an SL-closed in L .

Proof: Clear from Theorem 5.

Theorem 7: Let $I \in \text{Id}(L)$ be a SL-complement in L and $J \in \text{Id}(L)$ be a SL-complement in L for some ideal in I . Then $I \cap J$ is an SL-closed ideal of L .

Proof: Let an ideal $K \subseteq I$ with J an SL-complement of K in L . Then by Theorem 6, $I \cap J$ is an SL-complement of K in I . Since I is an SL-complement in L , we have Corollary 1, that $I \cap J$ is an SL-closed ideal of L .

Theorem 8: Let L be a modular lattice. Let $I, J, K \in \text{Id}(L)$ be such that $L = I \oplus J$, $K \subseteq I$ and $P \in \text{Id}(L)$ an SL-complement of $K \oplus J$ in L . If $P \subseteq I$ then P is an SL-complement of K in L .

Proof: Since $P \oplus (K \oplus J)$ is strongly large in L , By Lemma 3, $[P \oplus (K \oplus J)] \cap I$ is strongly large in I . By modularity condition we have, $[P \oplus (K \oplus J)] \cap I = [I \cap (K \oplus J)] \oplus P = [K \oplus (I \cap J)] \oplus P = K \oplus P$. So I is a strongly large extension of $K \oplus P$. Since P is SL-closed in L and P is SL-closed in I . Therefore P is an SL-complement of K in I .

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the Vice-Chancellor Research Motivation Scheme (VCRMS) under grant through K.B.C.N.M. University Fund.

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